

Evaluation Of Social Studies Curriculum Implementation for the Attainment Of Citizenship Education Among Students Of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated evaluation of social studies curriculum implementation for the attainment of citizenship education among junior secondary school students of Sokoto State, Nigeria. It was conducted with the objectives to; determine the extent to which social studies curriculum contents has helped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State ; examine the extent to which social studies teachers are equipped for the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State; examine the extent to which available instructional materials can be utilized in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State; assess how social studies learning environment can help in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State; and ascertain the extent to which social studies teaching methods are effectively used for the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State. Five corresponding research questions were raised, while five null hypotheses were formulated for test. The study was a survey research design. A total of 12 teachers and 372 students were sampled for the study using random sampling technique. Data was collected using a researcher designed instrument tagged “Social Studies Curriculum Implementation Questionnaire (SSCIQ) Data gathered were analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation while all the null hypotheses were tested using chi-square statistics at 0.05% alpha level of significance. Findings among others showed that significant difference exists between the social studies curriculum contents and the extent to which citizenship education can be attained by students in Sokoto State. Result also revealed that there is no significant difference between low equipped social studies teachers and the attainment of citizenship education by students in Sokoto State. Based on the findings, recommendations were made that, Social studies teachers with requisite academic qualification and enduring years of experience should be allowed to effectively implement the Social Studies curriculum contents in order to attain citizenship education in Sokoto State. Also, Social studies teachers should be adequately equipped so as to attain citizenship education by students in Sokoto State.

Keywords: Social studies curriculum, citizenship education, learning environment

INTRODUCTION

The driving force behind all human development (that is, social, economic, political and technological) and in fact civilization is “education”. This implies that education is anchored on a solid and time-tested foundation capable of relieving man from the cold hands of ignorance, poverty,

diseases, squalor and unemployment, intellectual and technological backwardness as it is the case with developing nations including Nigeria. According to Audu (2002), the products of any educational system should be reasonably empowered, to exert some element of control over the events that affect them through efficient and functional education. This will greatly be attainable if education is relevant to the needs, desires and aspirations of the society, thereby leading to the development of individuals and the entire society at large through the acquisition of appropriate knowledge, skills, ideas, values, attitudes, competencies and abilities. All these are consequent upon change owing to dynamic nature of the society to meet societal challenges and stand the test of time.

The National Policy on Education (2009), re-affirms keeping the dynamics of social changes with the demands on education, with some policy innovation and changes in the educational system. Thus, the Federal Government of Nigeria after independence till date has been involved in constant reforms of Nigeria educational policy(s) to meet the dynamism of social changes as it affects the needs, desires and aspiration of the immediate and global society. According to Fafunwa (2009), Nigeria on attainment of independence inherited an educational system that lacks relevance in meeting the pressing economic, social and cultural needs of the country. He observed this during the bi-annual meeting of Joint Consultative Committee (JCC), a national advisory committee held at Enugu in 1964. This he asserts "After five years of Nigerian independence, the educational system of the country was colonial, more British than British themselves (p.239)". That is to say that, the Nigerian school children were being educated to meet the needs of a foreign culture and was therefore better fit for it than the demands of their own country. The implication of this situation on the Nigerian society is the irrelevance of that education to meet the needs and desires of the country in terms of manpower development and the acquisition of relevant skills, values and attitudes needed to move the country forward. This led to massive criticism of the then educational system by the public and this consequently led to the proposal of the 1969 national curriculum conference held between 8-12 September at Lagos. Apparently, since the colonial era in Nigeria, the inculcation of the right type of values has become a major concern of the educational system. This concern has become more persuasive after independence right up to the present. To train citizens, there must be a sense of belonging, equity and fairness, particularly among teachers who are strategically placed in the whole process of citizenship education in conjunction with the community. Culture is dynamic, but basic ideas are constant. Cultural differences do not enable us to have open mind on things that border on national issues. Mistrust and sectionalism persist despite all efforts to break the barriers. Hence, Social studies is interested in bringing up a whole personality in line with the dominant values, aspirations, beliefs and culture of the Nigerian society, so that the recipient become useful to themselves and to the wider society. As a Social Studies educator, concerned with citizenship education, the researcher has been interested in trying to empirically verify some of the claims made about the relationship between Social Studies and citizenship training because of the need to re-assess the contribution a subject can make to the education of young people, particularly Social Studies which is relatively new in the Nigerian educational system. The proper and legitimate contribution which Social Studies has to offer a child can be considered in relation to the

Ultimate purpose of education in Nigeria. A closer look at the national objectives as set out in the National Policy on Education would help throw some light on the contributions that Social Studies as a discipline can make in achieving these set goals. Nigeria's philosophy of education is based on the integration of the individual as a sound effective citizen and equal educational opportunities for all citizens at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels. In view of this, the success of training effective citizens for the nation depends on the teacher and the learning environment. Every school subject is expected to contribute to the citizens' education. If the Nigerian national goals (FGN, 2009) of building a free, democratic, just and egalitarian society, a united strong and self-reliant nation, a great and dynamic economy and a land of bright and full of opportunities for all citizens are to be achieved. For effective citizenship teaching/learning to take place, the teacher should be professionally competent and dedicated. This is important because part of the possibility for the achievement of these goals largely rests on the quality of the teacher's input and output as well as his method of teaching. This therefore depends on the teacher's ability to teach mastery of the knowledge of Social Studies content and methodology, the availability and proper use of appropriate and relevant instructional materials.

Social Studies in the contemporary Nigeria context, according to Tikuma (2009), posit that it surfaced in 1958 in western region when the subject was introduced into schools through a joint educational programme between the region and the University of Ohio (USA) "the Ohio project" as it was tagged only affected the western region. In 1963 a pilot project was conducted at Aiyetoro comprehensive school. This venture led to a comprehensive development of the first Nigerian Social Studies curriculum at the said school. Tikuma (2009) noted that subsequent upon the introduction in the western region was a series of curriculum innovation conferences that was held locally and internationally. This among others includes the conference of African educators held in Mombasa (Kenya) in 1968. This conference was organized under the auspices of the education development center (EDC) and the centre for curriculum renewal and education/development overseas (CREDO). This conference drew eleven participants from African countries including Nigeria. From this conference emerged African Social Studies Programme (ASSP) and later the Nigerian Social Studies Programme (NSSP). Subsequent on the Mombasa conference in 1968, Nigeria accelerated her march towards entrenching Social Studies in her education system. Thus, in January 1969 participants were drawn from all over Nigeria to Ibadan for a seminar in Social Studies except the eastern part of the country which was then a threat of war. Social Studies Association of Nigeria (SOSAN) was formed at this seminar and the objective of the association includes the dissemination, promotion, development and adoption of Social Studies in Nigerian schools. Equally in 1969, a national curriculum conference was held in Lagos where large participants were drawn from all the nooks and crannies of the Nigerian society vis-a-vis, doctors, traders, farmers, teachers, business-men and so forth, to discuss issues of ideology, purpose and objectives of Nigerian education. There SOSAN presented a report on the need for the introduction of Social Studies. The resolution and recommendation of the conference touched on the teaching of culture and Social Studies in the Nigerian Educational system i.e Social Studies should be taught in all teacher training colleges and in the lower classes of the secondary school and primary schools. Thus, the deliberation and recommendation of the conference and seminars forms the pivot of the Federal Government National Policy on Education in 1977. Thus, Ismail in Aliyu (2009), in his statement rose that social studies was introduced on a national basis at the 1 969 national curriculum conference.

Objectives of Social Studies Education in Nigeria

The reasons for teaching Social Studies and what we teach in it is a fulcrum to which the success of the entire programme is built upon. Social studies was introduced into Nigerian schools system as a remedy to existing social problems prevalent in the society. It aims at studying social actions, relationship, addressing social needs and problems. The objectives of social studies vary from one country to another; this is dependent on the situation and conditions of the country adopting it. Thus, there are varieties of objectives of Social Studies as there are varieties of social needs and problems (Tikuma, 2009). Argungu (2009) posited that, social studies as stated earlier was introduced into Nigerian schools as a core and compulsory subject at primary and junior secondary schools as a catalyst to the achievement of the four national educational aims and objectives. Obameata, Agu and Laosebikan in Argungu (2009), explained that the objectives of Social Studies in Nigeria naturally reflect the national objectives of education as a whole. This is basically on the premise that Social Studies, is a subject that draws its concepts from all the basic subjects at the primary and secondary levels of education such as History, Government, Economics, Religion among others, Based on this, the objectives of social studies tend to reflect the objectives of these subjects. Secondly, the subject is designed to offer specific solutions to societal issues or offer remedy to national problems. Thus its objectives must be relatively interwoven with national goals of education if it is to answer this call. The national educational goals as presented by the national policy on education (2009) states the following:

- a. The inculcation of national consciousness and national unity
- b. The inculcation of the right types of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society.
- c. The training of the mind in the understanding of the world around and
- d. The acquisition of the appropriate skills and the development of mental, physical and social abilities and competencies as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of his society.

It is based on these goals that the objectives of Social Studies were designed. According to Ololobou (2004) a typical social studies programme must encompass four cardinal objectives namely the environment, the various skills, values and skills and emerging issues. Equally in his work, Ololobou (1999), observed that Social Studies in Nigeria seeks to re-establish the pre-colonial African educational values, which includes honesty, hard-work, mutual cooperation and conformity to traditional social order. NERDC, in Ikwumelu (2000) categorized the objectives into the Following;

Statement of the Problem

Social Studies education is a programme of studies introduced into the Nigerian Educational curriculum to offer partial solutions to social and attitudinal problems facing the country. This is meant to be achieved through the inculcation of desired positive values, attitudes and social skills to learners of Social Studies in the primary, junior secondary and the teachers training colleges in Nigeria. This discipline or programme of study is meant to achieve the objectives of national unity, national consciousness, self-reliance and national reconstruction which are the basis for the national goals of education in Nigeria. These could be achieved through effective inculcation of positive values, ideas, beliefs and knowledge that can enhance the change in the behaviour of learners in the desired direction. The learners of social studies therefore, are expected to be drilled and baptized in the etiquette of social studies education, become more of a social fanatic in the principles of social studies education. Their ways of life, thinking, actions and values should be in conformity to the expectation of social studies for self-development and social re-engineering. Thus expecting a society free of social and attitudinal problems if effectively and efficiently implemented.

Social studies education has not been properly implemented in the schools to equip students with the knowledge, facts and ideas that can enhance positive values and attitudes for the survival of individuals and the society. These social problems range from disrespect to elders and constituted authority chronic dishonesty, corruption, religions crises, ethnic/tribal crises, murder, arson, examination malpractices, drug abuse, cultism, indiscipline and other forms of mal-adaptive behaviour. Adeyoyin and Okam cited in Livingstone (2011) confirmed that the classroom dispensation of citizenship education amongst students has not sufficiently "Nigerianized" them into becoming effective and productive individual or citizens within the context of Nigeria as a young democracy. These critics argued that this development has not only failed to ameliorate ethnocentrism amongst learners but has failed to stimulate in them an awareness about the importance of developing a sense of loyalty to the nation. Similarly, in using effective method to train citizens, the teacher must have the necessary professional background and conducive working environment including welfare as well as opportunities for further studies, however, even if the above conditions present themselves, and the teachers do not have the right attitudes towards citizenship training, it is doubtful if much can be achieved in that direction. This therefore mean that teachers, who will transform youths from different parochial cultural and social backgrounds into well socialized and integrated Nigerians, must themselves believe in one Nigeria and be committed to its continuity and development as a nation. The consequences of the above scenario might explain why the process of citizenship training has not been able to satisfactorily curb antisocial behaviours based on irrational decision making by the products of the system. Also, with respect to teaching methods, the classroom trend in citizenship education which emphasizes achievements and acquisition of objectives associated with the "Cognitive Domain" while objective impinge on the "Affective and Psychomotor Domains" are neglected. This study was consequently prompted by the fact that ineffective evaluation of social studies education is responsible for disappearing values and attitudinal change among school children, youth and adults of our society, thus an evaluation of the junior secondary school social studies education curriculum implementation in Sokoto State will become relevant.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are stated as follows: To

1. evaluate the extent to which social studies curriculum contents has helped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State;
2. examine the extent to which social studies teachers are equipped for the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State;
3. determine the extent to which available instructional materials can be utilized in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State;

4. assess how social studies learning environment can help in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State; and
5. ascertain the extent to which social studies teaching methods are effectively used for the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State.

Research Questions

This study will attempt to find answers to the following research questions. These are:

1. To what extent has social studies curriculum content helped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State?
2. To what extent are social studies teachers equipped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State?
3. To what extent are the available instructional materials used in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State?
4. How has social studies learning environment help in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State?
5. To what extent are the social studies teaching methods effectively used for the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State?

Hypotheses

The study has formulated the following null-hypotheses which shall be tested at 0.05 level of significance for acceptance or otherwise.

1. There is no significant difference between the social studies curriculum contents and extent to which citizenship education can be attained by students in Sokoto State.
2. There is no significant difference between the equipped social studies teachers and the attainment of citizenship education by students in Sokoto State.
3. There is no significant difference between the extents to which available instructional materials can be utilized in the attainment of citizenship education by students in Sokoto State.
4. There is no significant difference between social studies learning environment and the attainment of citizenship education by students in Sokoto State.
6. There is no significant difference between the effective use of social studies teaching methods and the attainment of citizenship education by students in Sokoto State.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter described the procedure that was employed in the conduct of the research work. The following sub-headings have been examined: Research design, population, sample and sampling techniques, instruments for data collection, validation of the instrument, pilot study, reliability of the instrument, procedure for data collection and procedure for data analysis respectively. The survey research design was adopted for this study. This research design permits the gathering of information through the use of questionnaire from a sample population based on appropriate sampling techniques. According to Barton and Baumann (2004), survey research provides a way in which to gather information on a large subset group of individuals and then make inferences to much larger groups. This design is relevant to this research work as it enables the researcher to describe an event, situation or phenomenon as it is at the time of the study (Francis, 2003) The population of the study is made up of social studies teachers and students of junior secondary schools in Sokoto state. There are seven (7) educational zones in the state spread across the three (3) senatorial zones of Sokoto Central, East and South respectively. A total number of three hundred and eighty-eight (388) public junior secondary schools exist in Sokoto state with teachers population (Social Studies) put at two hundred and thirty (230) and students population of eight thousand, eight hundred and thirty-six (8,836). However, the target population for this study is four hundred and fifty (450) respondents mainly teachers and students from and Educational zones of the state. Table 3.1 present the population distribution for the study.

Table 1: Population of Teachers and Students from Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State

SN	Zones	No. of Sch.	No. of Male Teachers	No. of Female Teachers	No. of Male Students	No. of Female Students
1.	Gwadabawa	26	26	12	386	157
2.	Bodinga	18	17	8	401	82
3.	Tambuwal	15	21	6	1,150	173
4.	Isa	17	16	7	816	97
5.	Wamakko	105	31	18	2411	706
6.	Wurno	14	12	3	431	121
7.	Sokoto Central	193	32	21	1780	125
Total		388	155	75	7,375	1,461

Source: Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education Sokoto 2025

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample size of three hundred and eighty-four (384) respondents was drawn at random from a target population of nine thousand, two hundred and twenty-four (9,224). These include social studies teachers and JSS II students from educational zones of Sokoto state. Out of the selected sample size of 388, two hundred (200) respondents were selected from Sokoto Central and Wamakko zones, another one hundred (100) from Gwadabawa and Wurno zones and one hundred and eighty-four (184) respondents from Bodinga and Tambuwal zones. Twenty (20) sampled schools were selected and from the 384 respondents selected from the educational zones, twelve (12) teachers and three hundred and seventy-two (372) students were selected. By simple random sampling techniques, it gives an equal and independent chance of the respondents been selected for this study. This was done using hat and drawn method. The schools selected for this study were selected across the different parts of the educational zones except for security challenge areas Sokoto East education zone..

Table 2 Sample Distribution of Respondents

Zone	No. of Sample Sch	No. of Male Teachers Sampled	No. of Female Teachers Sampled	No. of Male Students Sample	No. of Female Students Sample
Sokoto Central	10	4	3	150	52
Bodinga	8	2	1	85	10
Wurno	2	1	1	65	10
Total	20	7	5	300	72

Source: Field work August 2025

Instrumentation

For the purpose of data collection, a researcher made questionnaire tagged “Social Studies Curriculum Implementation Questionnaire (SSCIQ)” was used to solicit for respondents’ opinion on evaluation of social studies curriculum implementation for the attainment of citizenship education among junior secondary school students of Sokoto State. This instrument was divided into two (2) sections namely section A and B. Section A sought to elicit personal information of the respondents and B was prepared along side the key variables of the research topic. The said questionnaire was scored using the modified Likert four point rating scale of strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagreed (D) respectively. In order to make sure that the final copy of the Social Studies Curriculum Implementation Questionnaire (SSCIQ) is valid, the researcher submitted the questionnaire to the supervisor and experts in Curriculum and Instruction Section, Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto, for scrutiny. Their criticisms and comments were reflected in the final draft of the questionnaire. A pilot study was conducted in Alheri Schools Sokoto and Caliphate International Schools Sokoto. These areas are not part of the study area but was chosen to determine the adequacy and effectiveness of the instrument in measuring what it is supposed to measure, and to ascertain any difficulty that the researcher may

encounter when carrying out the main study. A total of twenty (20) copies of the questionnaire was administered on the subjects for the pilot study.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The analysis and interpretation of data collected through the questionnaire and interview adopted in the collection of data for this study. In the course of the analyses of data, tables of frequencies and percentages were used. The demographic characteristics of the students and teachers were presented in tables under the column of frequencies and percentages. The responses of the students and teachers who were the respondents in this study formed the basis for the analysis of data in this chapter. Consequently, the analysis was presented in phases or sections. The first section of this chapter presents the frequency and percentages of the bio-data variables which included status, gender, age, marital status, and qualification. The second section presents the answers to research questions using comparative mean and standard deviations. The third section presents and interprets the five null hypotheses structured along the research objectives by means of nonparametric statistical technique of Independent chi-square to determine the presence or absence of significant differences for all the four hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested on 0.05 alpha level of significance. The fourth section outlined the major findings of the study and the last section discussed the findings of the study in detail.

Table 3: Qualifications of the respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage %
Students	372	90.4
SSCE	2	6.0
NCE	5	1.3
B.Ed	3	0.8
B.Ed	1	0.2
M.Sc/M.Ed and above	1	0.2
Total	384	100

Source: Field Survey July, 2025

Table 3 shows that, 372 or 96.9% of the respondents are students, while 2 or 0.5% of the respondents are SSCE holders, NCE holders with 5 or 1.3% as holders of Bachelors degree in education. Likewise, 2 or 0.5% have qualifications in Bachelor of Education degree and the few 3 or 0.8% . While 0.2% are holders of Bachelor of Science, Masters of Science, Master of Education and above.

Research Question One: To what extent has social studies curriculum content helped in the attainment of citizenship among students of Junior Secondary Schools of Sokoto State?

Table 4.5 revealed the opinions of teachers and students on the extent to which social studies curriculum content helped in the attainment of citizenship among students of Junior Secondary Schools of Sokoto State.

Table 4.: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question One

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	2.402	2.03
Students	372	4.317	3.01
Total	384	3.4	2.52
Decision Mean 2.5			

Analysis of the above table presents the opinions of teachers and students on a number of item statements as contained in the questionnaire. This table revealed that the total mean of 3.4 was higher than the decision mean of 2.5. By this result, social studies curriculum content helped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State.

Research Question Two: *To what extent are social studies teachers equipped in the attainment of citizenship education among Students in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state?*

Table 4.6 shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent to which social studies teachers are equipped in the attainment of citizenship education among Students in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state.

Table 5: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question Two

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	1.4396	1.0955
Students	372	2.69	1.1679
Total	384	2.1	1.1317
Decision Mean		2.5	

Table 4.6 depicts the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the extent to which social studies teachers are equipped in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. The table revealed that the total mean of 2.1 was lower than the decision mean of 2.5. This result shows that social studies teachers are not well equipped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State.

Research Question Three: *How adequate are instructional materials used in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?*

Table 6. presents the opinions of the respondents regarding the adequate instructional materials used in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Table 6: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question Three

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	2.32	0.173
Students	372	2.10	1.14
Total	384	2.2	0.6565

Decision Mean 2.5

Table .6 shows the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the instructional materials used in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto state educational zone. The table revealed that the total mean of 2.2 was lower than the decision mean of 2.5. This means that the instructional materials used in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State are not adequate. Majority of the respondents were of the opinion that modern instructional materials like radio, television, tap recorder, projector, slides, computer, video, decoder, and camera are not used at all by social studies teachers while the few of them greed that charts and textbooks are more often used while teaching social studies. Also, some of the respondents agreed that pictures and diagrams are often used (see Appendix B. III).

Research Question Four: *How conducive is social studies learning environment in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?*

Table 7: revealed the opinions of the respondents on social studies learning environment in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Table 7: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question Four

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	2.68	1.1679
Students	372	2.7396	1.0955
Total	384	2.71	1.1317

Decision Mean 2.5

Table 7 revealed the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the social studies learning environment in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.. The table revealed that the total mean of 2.71 was higher than the decision mean of 2.5. This means that social studies learning environment has relationship with the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.. Therefore, the respondents were of the view that they often use classroom, library, playing ground and assembly hall, while enough windows, lightening and toilet are not adequately provided and are rarely used.

Research Question Five: *To what extent are social studies teaching methods helped for the attainment of citizenship education?*

Table 8. revealed the extent to which social studies teaching methods helped in the attainment of citizenship education.

Table 8: Summary of respondents' opinion in respect to Research Question Five

Respondents	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	12	2.61	0.698
Students	372	2.9831	1.0891
Total	384	2.8	0.894

Decision Mean 2.5

Table 4.9 revealed the result of analysis of respondents' opinion on the extent to which social studies teaching methods helped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State. The table revealed the total mean of 2.8 which was higher than the decision mean of 2.5. This means that social studies teaching methods helped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State. Based on the opinions gathered, it was revealed that discussion, questioning, lecture and demonstration methods are found to be effective as they are more often used, while story telling and inquiry are often used. Also, finding shows that modeling, and play role are rarely used.

Hypotheses Testing

All the five null hypotheses were tested at alpha 0.05 level of significance using chi square statistics.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the social studies curriculum contents and the extent to which citizenship education can be attained by students. Table 4.10 revealed the opinions of teachers and students on the social studies curriculum contents and the extent to which citizenship education can be attained by students.

Table .9: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between the social studies curriculum contents and the extent to which citizenship education can be attained by students

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX ₂	α	df	CritiX ₂	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	2.402	2.03	21.47	0.05	5	12.43	0.001	Rejected
Students	372	4.317	3.01						
Total	384	3.4	2.52						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

Results of the chi-square statistics on table 4.10 revealed that $P < 0.05$ because the X^2 obtained (21.47) is greater than critical X^2 (12.43), this means that there is a significant difference between the social studies curriculum contents and the extent to which citizenship education can be attained by students in Sokoto State. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between low equipped social studies teachers and the attainment of citizenship education by students in Sokoto State.

Table .10 shows the opinions of teachers and students in respect of the difference between low equipped social studies teachers and the attainment of citizenship education by students.

Table .10: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between low equipped social studies teachers and the attainment of citizenship education by students

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX ₂	α	df	CritiX ₂	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	1.439	1.0955	9.245	0.05	5	15.391	0.710	Retained
Students	372	2.69	1.1679						
Total	384	2.1	1.1317						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

The result on table 4.11 shows that X^2 calculated of 9.245 was less than the critical X^2 of 15.391 under 5 df, under 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X^2 was less than the critical X^2 , the decision was to accept the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between low equipped social studies teachers and the attainment of citizenship education by students.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between social studies education and the use of instructional materials by teachers towards the attainment of citizenship education by students.

Table 11 shows the opinions of teachers and students on the difference between social studies education and the use of instructional materials by teachers towards the attainment of citizenship education by students.

Table .11: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between social studies education and the use of instructional materials by teachers towards the attainment of citizenship education by students.

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX ₂	α	df	CritiX ₂	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	2.32	0.173	18.20	0.05	4	26.412	0.217	Retained
Students	372	2.10	1.14						
Total	384	2.2	0.6565						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

Table .11 shows that X^2 calculated of 18.20 was less than the critical X^2 of 26.412 under df of 4, and 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X^2 was less than the critical X^2 , the decision was to accept the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between social studies education and the use of instructional materials by teachers towards the attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference between social studies learning environment and the attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Table .11: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between social studies learning environment and the attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX ₂	α	df	CritiX ₂	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	2.68	1.1679	10.59	0.05	4	4.617	0.004	Rejected
Students	372	2.739	1.0955						
Total	384	2.71	1.1317						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

Table 4.13 shows that X₂ calculated of 10.59 was higher than the critical X₂ of 4.617 under df of 4, and 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X₂ was higher than the critical X₂, the decision was to reject the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between social studies learning environment and the attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant difference between social studies teaching methods and attainment of citizenship education by students by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Table 12: Summary of the non-parametric statistics (chi-square) on the difference between social studies teaching methods and attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Respondents	N	X	SD	CalX ₂	α	df	CritiX ₂	P-value	Decision
Teachers	12	2.61	0.698	19.27	0.05	5	5.919	0.001	Rejected
Students	372	2.983	1.0891						
Total	384	2.8	0.894						

Source: Fieldwork (2025).

Table 4.14 revealed the X₂ calculated of 19.27 which is higher than the critical X₂ of 5.919 under df of 5, and 0.05 alpha level of significance. Since the calculated X₂ was higher than the critical X₂, the decision was to reject the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between social studies teaching methods and attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Summary of Major Findings

The following are the findings of the study based on the hypotheses tested:

1. Finding revealed a significant difference between the social studies curriculum contents and the extent to which citizenship education can be attained by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
2. Finding revealed that there is no significant difference between low equipped social studies teachers and the attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
3. Finding from the study showed no significant difference between social studies education and the use of instructional materials by teachers towards the attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State..
4. Finding revealed also revealed no significant difference between social studies learning environment and the attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
5. Result shows that there is no significant difference between social studies teaching methods and attainment of citizenship education by students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

CONCLUSION

In view of the findings from this study, conclusion were drawn that; social studies curriculum content helped in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State and that social studies teachers are not well equipped in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State. It was also concluded that instructional materials used in the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State are not adequate. Similarly, social studies learning environment has relationship with the attainment of citizenship education in Sokoto State; and that social studies teaching methods helped in the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made in view of the findings from this study that:

1. Social studies teachers with requisite academic qualification and enduring years of experience should be allowed to effectively implement the Social Studies curriculum contents in order to attain citizenship education in Sokoto State.
2. Social studies teachers should be adequately equipped so as to attain citizenship education by students in Sokoto State.
3. Social studies teachers should be encouraged on the use of instructional materials towards the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
4. Government should make sure that all the school facilities such as instructional, recreational, residential and general-purpose facilities be provided for the attainment of citizenship education among students of Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
5. Training and re-training of staff especially those of Social Studies teachers should be encouraged in order to acquire new methods of teaching the subject.

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REFERENCES

- Abdulkareem, A.Y. (2006). *A study of Teachers; and student's perception on social studies and Teaching Methods in social studies in selected Grade II Teachers' Colleges in the Northern States of Nigeria*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, ABU, Zaria, Nigeria.
- Abok, A. D. (1996). *Teacher-Trainee Evaluation of the Adequacy of the NCCE Social Studies Programme for Citizenship Transmission*. Unpublished Ph.D Dissertation A.B.U Zaria.
- Abubakar, I.D. (2009). *Evaluation of the Implementation of Nomadic Primary School Social Studies Programme in Nigeria: Implication for Curriculum Renewal*. An Unpublished P.hD Dissertation A.B.U Zaria.
- Adekeye, (1996). *An Evaluation of the NCE Social Studies Programme of Institute of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria*. An Unpublished MED Thesis A.B.U. Zaria.
- Adoke, I. (1997). *A Study of Teacher and Students Perception Teaching Methods in Social Studies in Selected Junior Secondary Schools in the Northern States of the Nigeria*. An Unpublished M. Ed thesis A.B.U Zaria.
- Aguokogbuo C. N. (2002). Problems and prospect of Secondary School Curriculum in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 9 (2), 92 – 97.
- Aina, N. E., Adeyoyin, F. A., Obilo, E.E. & Ahmadu, U.S. (2000). *Social Studies. A Book on Methodology*. Ibadan: Evans Brothers.
- Aina, N.F. (1981). *Social Studies: A Book on Methodology*. Ibadan, Evans Brothers.
- Akande, M.D. (1987). General Principles of Teaching in Fagbanuye E.O. (eds) *Introduction to Education*. University of Logos Series in Education, Lagos Welson Publishers Ltd.
- Akinlaye, F.A. (1998). *Fundamentals of Social Studies Teaching*. Ibadan Variety Publication Ltd.
- Alih, A. M. (2002). Education for self Sustenance: The case of Integrated Social Studies in Nigeria Schools and College. *Ankpa Journal of Arts and Social Science* Vol 1 No 2
- Aliyu, S. (2009). Assessment of the Implementation of Social Studies Programme in Nigeria; A Factor analysis. *Journal of Higher Education*, 44 (7), 5-9

- Aliyu, Y. A. (2009). *Assessment of the implementation of Social studies curriculum in primary schools in Kano metropolis*. A Thesis submitted to the Postgraduate school, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Amdii, V. L. (2004). *Social Studies As An Instrument for Social Value Acquisition in Nigeria: Perception of social Studies of the University of Abuja* in Oderinde, B. B and Ekpo, O. E. (eds) *Values in Education*. Lagos: Olu-Akin printing Press.
- Argungu, M. A. (2009). *Understanding Social Studies; "A Guide to Students and Teachers*. Zaria: Yaliam PRESS.
- Audu, N. (2002). *Development and utilization in the Service of Education in Contemporary Nigeria; Implication for National Development* *Appreciation of the School of Education*. Kogi State College of Education Ankpa.
- Azodo C. J. (1999). *Science Education in Nigeria. Emerging issues and Challenges for the 21st Century*. STAN 1999 (15 – 18).
- Balyejusa, P.N. (1981). *The Nature and Scope of Social Studies" in the Concept and Scope of Social Studies Education for Schools and Colleges*. Lagos: NERDC.
- Barton, J. J., & Baumann, J. F. (2004). *Survey research*. In N. K. Duke & M. H. Mallette (Eds.), *Literacy research methodologies* (pp. 287-307). New York: The Guilford Press.
- Ben-Yunus, M. (2000). *Issues on Curriculum*. Zaria: Yag Enterprises.
- Ben-Yunusa M. (2008). *Issues on Curriculum 3rd Edition*. Zaria: Sankore, Educational Publisher ABU, Zaria.
- Busari, O. O. (1988). *Problems and remedies of Implementing the Junior secondary School Social studies curricular in Nigeria*. *JORIC*, 4(17).
- Dubey, D.L. & Barth, J.E. (2000). *Social Studies in Inquiry Method Approach*: Lagos Nelson African.
- Fafunwa, (1974). *History of Education in Nigeria*. London: George Allen and Unwin Ltd.
- Fafunwa, A.B. (2008). *History of Education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: N. P. S Educational Publisher, Ltd.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National Policy on Education* (4th Edition). Abuja.
- Francis, A. (2003). *Ethical Dilemmas in International Mediation*, *Negotiation Journal* 11:333- 336.
- Fubara V. R. (2008). *Teaching methods, instructional materials and resources in social Studies in Nigeria* (ed) Owerri: Accadapeak publishers.
- Galadima, M. S. (2000). *Teachers Assessment of the Impact of Social Studies Education on the development of effective Citizenship: A Case Study of Chanchaga local government area of Niger state-Nigeria*. M.Ed Thesis work submitted to ABU, Zaria.
- Gottan, C. T. (2004). *An Evaluation of the Christian Religion Knowledge Curriculum for Junior Secondary School in Plateau State of Nigeria*. Unpublished P.hD Thesis, university of Jos.86
- Greenward, G.E. Bridge, I.M. Wake W.B & Mctera, J.E (1979). *Tudent Evaluation of College Teaching behavious instrument: A Factor analysis*. *Journal of Higher Education*, 44 (18) pp596-604.